

Disparity of Healthcare and Medicine in Rural India

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Abstract

Over the past ten years, India's population has experienced considerable improvements in health, narrowing the gap between rural and urban areas as well as between the wealthy and the poor. However, there are still significant gaps, and it is still quite difficult for people in rural areas to receive healthcare. India's rural inhabitants have extremely limited access to healthcare services. The government spends little on healthcare and what it does spend is primarily allocated to urban areas rather than rural ones. In addition, the private healthcare sector mostly caters to urban areas. India suffers from a severe scarcity of healthcare professionals, but rural areas are severely affected. India accounts for 20% of the world's illness burden and 17% of its population. According to infant mortality statistics, there are significant differences between rural and urban areas. Villages account for 82 percent of all habitation. Only 28% of the population is served by doctors, who make up 74% of the population. Residents of rural areas continue to lack access to medical care. A country like India, which has insufficient social security institutions and very little public investment in the health sector, is demographically burdened by the ageing population. The difference in older Indians' access to healthcare services between rural and urban areas is a problem that comes along with the country's rapid demographic change. As a result, this review attempts to explore the key contributing elements that account for the disparity between rural and urban older Indians' use of healthcare.

Keywords

Healthcare, Rural, Urban, Population, Private health sector

Introduction

Healthcare in India has developed a lot from earlier years to decrease the disparity between urban and rural areas. But there are still disparities which haven't been solved yet. Many economic factors such as age, gender and income as well as other factors are involved (Basu, 2022). HealthCare in rural India still remains a huge problem. This review paper will discuss on current disparities, reasons behind it and how they can be solved.

The health status of its people could change thanks to India's strong economic growth, expanding rural infrastructure, and access to technology. Some state governments have created and implemented creative methods to deal with the issues of healthcare availability and affordability. To increase access, adaptability, and quality of primary healthcare, many not-for-profit organizations that operate in remote, hard-to-reach locations have innovated. There are also significant, extensive case studies of numerous nations that have dealt with the issue of providing universal, first-rate healthcare to the most underserved groups (Sivakumar I, Manimekalai K & Ranjithkumar A, 2020). The health status of its people could change thanks to India's strong economic growth, expanding rural infrastructure, and access to technology. Some state governments have created and implemented creative methods to deal with the issues of healthcare availability and affordability.

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Background

A country like India, which has insufficient social security institutions and very little public investment in the health sector, is demographically burdened by the ageing population. The difference in older Indians' access to healthcare services between rural and urban areas is a problem that comes along with the country's rapid demographic change. To "progressively achieve universal health coverage," one of the key goals of India's National Health Policy (2017), it is necessary to understand the factors contributing to sub-national disparities in order to implement targeted policy interventions. As a result, this study attempts to explore the key contributing elements that account for the disparity between rural and urban older Indians' use of healthcare (Sivakumar I, Manimekalai K & Ranjithkumar A, 2020).

It is crucial to investigate primary care disparities because, according to research, primary care may mitigate the detrimental impacts of economic disparity on mortality and health, particularly in regions with the highest levels of income inequality. For instance, a United Nations report claims that only 27% of India's population resides in metropolitan regions, but 75% of the country's health infrastructure—including doctors, specialists, and other health resources—is concentrated. There is a persistent dearth of appropriate medical services in India's rural areas, which are home to 716 million people (72% of the country's population). According to earlier research, there is no other economic sector that is experiencing a crisis as severe as rural health care in India (Thayyil J & Jeeja M., 2013).

India's economy is expanding quickly, its rural infrastructure is getting better, and its people have access to technology, all of which have the potential to improve the country's population's health. Some state governments have created and implemented creative methods to deal with the issues of healthcare availability and affordability. To increase access, responsiveness, and quality of basic healthcare, many not-for-profit organizations that operate in remote, hard-to-reach locations have innovated. There are also significant, extensive case studies of numerous nations that have dealt with the issue of providing universal, first-rate healthcare to the most underserved groups (Sivakumar I, Manimekalai K & Ranjithkumar A, 2020).

These experiences can inform and direct the implementation of India's policy objectives. To identify the components that could direct India's efforts to improve healthcare in rural and underserved areas, a one-day national consultation was held to exchange lessons learned from experiences and evidence of rural primary healthcare in India and from across the world. The consultation was a component of the 2018 Global Rural Health Conference, which took place in New Delhi from April 26 to 29 (Thayyil J & Jeeja M., 2013).

Data source:

The dependent variable has been determined to be whether any treatments have been administered on medical recommendation (Yes = 1, No = 0). Information on the type of therapy obtained for illness periods throughout the previous 15 days recall period was gathered in the 75th round of the NSS. This covers both short-term and long-term illnesses (chronic and acute) that began during the previous 15 days as well as those that began more than 15 days ago but persisted during the recall period. In this study, all treatment categories other than "no treatment" were combined, resulting in the binary categories of "therapy sought" and "no treatment sought". Moreover, instances of reported self-treatment were reclassified as falling under the "no treatment" category (Basu, 2022).

The patient's gender, one of the risk variables, was frequently emphasized in the context of emerging nations with a sizable rural population. Past studies have demonstrated that, particularly in rural regions, the health care seeking behaviours of men and women differ. This is due to the fact that women, and especially female children, usually receive preventive care less frequently than males or may experience longer wait times for proper primary care in rural areas of various regions. One impact of this gap in access could be that rural women are admitted to hospitals more frequently for diseases that could be treated in the outpatient care unit or through care received in doctors' offices. Another impact could be that rural women will experience more Complex hospitalizations than rural men, which could increase their risk of impairment and demise. In the setting of a rural economy, the impact of gender prejudice on healthcare outcomes is a serious problem that requires more attention. Gender bias and inequalities could be thoroughly examined because they have a negative impact on patient outcomes for important medical care (Banerjee, 2021).

Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Janaushadhi Pariyojana (PMBJP)

Despite being one of the top suppliers of generic drugs globally, the majority of Indians do not have adequate access to inexpensive medications. The therapeutic value of branded (Generic) drugs is the same as that of their unbranded generic counterparts, despite the fact that they are sold at much higher prices. Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Janaushadhi Pariyojana (PMBJP) was established with the goal of providing excellent generic medications to everyone at reasonable prices, especially the underprivileged and impoverished. The year 2008 saw the Department's commencement of this programme. As part of this programme, special pharmacies known as Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Janaushadhi Kendras (PMBJK) are set up around the nation to offer generic medications to the general public.

Objectives of the Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Janaushadhi Pariyojana (PMBJP)

To lower patients' out-of-pocket expenses by making high-quality medicines, consumables, and surgical supplies available to everyone at affordable costs. To spread awareness about generic medications among the general public and refutethe myth that generic medications are of lower quality or less effective because they are more affordable. To make sure that all women in India can easily access menstrual health care. Create jobs by enlisting individual business owners in the launch of PMBJP Kendras.

Financial year	Yearly addition	cumulative	Sales at MRP value in Cr.
2014-15	14	86	7.29
2015-16	154	240	12.16
2016-17	720	960	32.66
2017-18	2233	3193	140.84
2018-19	1863	5056	315.70
2019-20	1250	6306	433.60

Number of PMBJPKendra functional units

What works for Rural Healthcare?**Family focused Healthcare**

There is strong support for the idea that family-centered care that emphasizes population health and provides comprehensive and ongoing treatment increases ruralcommunities' access to healthcare. Such treatment combines preventative and promotional care and is provided by medical professionals (doctors, nurses, and other healthcare workers) who are qualified to handle a variety of conditions, such as safe childbirths, cardiovascular conditions, and respiratory conditions. They receive additional training in teamwork, understanding community needs, and actively participating in them (Mohan P & Kumar R, 2019). India allocates a modest amount of its budget to healthcare. The majority of this improvement happened in rural areas, lowering health inequities, as a result of increased budgetary allocations to the National Rural Health Mission. The overall fiscal commitment to healthcare is still small, at just 1% of GDP, which limits the potential for development (Banerjee, 2021).

Higher Investment and Training Rural Healthcare Professionals

There is strong evidence in India that states with larger healthcare budget allocations achieve better health outcomes than states with lower budget allocations. In South Africa and Brazil, there are worries that decreased public spending on primary healthcare will make it more difficult to provide care to the most marginalized communities (Bhan N, Rao K D & Kachwaha S., 2016). According to data from around the world, such care is most efficiently delivered by healthcare professionals (particularly doctors and nurses) who have received training in comprehensive healthcare and are mentally equipped to give a full range of services to the rural community. Such training must take place in rural health facilities with trainees integrated into rural communities for it to be effective (Basu, 2022). Primary care or a generalist strategy Health care providers in rural locations must offer a variety of services for a wide range of ailments to people at all stages of life. As a result, they must possess a variety of clinical, interpersonal, and leadership abilities. Modern medical and nursing education is only focused on providing care in specialized tertiary care settings, where it is taught (Basu, 2022).

Strategy to be used for Analysis:

A mixed method analysis, in which quantitative data should be complemented with case studies and focus group talks within rural and urban areas of regions, would be the most effective approach for a large-scale study to address these challenges. The data gathered from published and unpublished sources, such as the World Health Organization, the Census, or other local sources, should be used in the computational analysis. To examine differences in socioeconomic parameters between rural and urban locations, statistical techniques like ANOVA and hypothesis testing should be applied when the data allow. Case studies and focus groups involving local scientists, public health authorities, operators of primary care clinics, and doctors will be part of the qualitative analytic method, which is anticipated to augment the analysis in cases when data will be unavailable. When one learns about the resources that are available and their constraints, the study's specifics will be adjusted (Banerjee, 2021).

Conclusion

Many health disparities are caused by a variety of social, economic, and political situations or elements that have an uneven impact on how well people are distributed across a community. The article provides a history and rationale for studies looking at rural-urban differences, particularly in terms of the use of primary care services. The essay summarizes a conceptual framework for future research as well. From this conceptual framework, a number of important research topics are deduced that can be investigated separately or collectively, by particular regions or local areas, individually or collectively, and in the context of developed or developing nations.

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